

ROAD TO ORGANIZATIONAL GREEN INNOVATION: CULTIVATING ROBUST GREEN PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL

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Abstract

The purpose of this scholarly analysis is to find out the way towards organizational green innovativeness through green transformational leadership in Pakistan's hotel sector presenting psychological contents in green wrapping as mediators and moderators. The multistage data collection technique has been used to analyze 283 responses through the SPSS process. The Sample was 500 hotel employees from five, four, and three-star hotels in Lahore, Pakistan. All level employees were the respondents. Analysis results revealed that there existed a strong, positive relationship between variables and it was found through correlation analysis. So accordingly, green transformational leadership has a significant relationship with green psychological empowerment, green psychological empowerment possesses a positive relationship with employee ecological behavior, and employee ecological behavior influences green organizational innovativeness as well. In a mediation case, green psychological empowerment does not mediate between green transformational leadership and green organizational innovativeness but employee ecological behavior mediates between green transformational leadership and green organizational innovativeness. As far as moderating variable green psychological capital (green team resilience and green self-efficacy) is concerned it plays a moderating role between employee ecological behavior and green organizational innovativeness. Practically, if transformational leadership under the green flag gave a chance to adopt and empower their employees, they will behave reciprocated and can lead the organization towards green innovativeness.

INTRODUCTION

The 21st century has been gifted with environmental distortion along with technological enhancements. Especially last 20 years have been known as environmental awareness years (Kim, Kim, Choi, & Phetvaroon, 2019) because resolving ecological issues

and turning organizations into green boundaries have become the main challenges of the era. (Paillé, Boiral, & Chen, 2013; Hall, Daneke, & Lenox, 2010). Therefore, in this pressurized scenario from the stakeholders' side, organizational concerns have been

turned towards conservational adaptation (Ababneh, 2021; Paillé & Boiral, 2013; Chen & Chang, 2013; W. Yu & Ramanathan, 2015; Yu, Ramanathan, & Nath, 2017) thus researchers (Elkins and Keller, 2003) have highlighted reliance for innovative purposes on transformational leadership. In a recent research study, the focus remained to understand resilience in which manners resilience can be operationalized in the leadership domain in organizations and can set practical approaches to address at the individual level to overcome challenges like adaptation, uncertainty, and other changes (M. Yu, Wen, Smith, & Stokes, 2022).

From a management perspective, dependency on intangible means is the only way to handle complications and pressures from outside and inside factors to attain green sustainability (Dubey, Gunasekaran, & Ali, 2015; Singh & El-Kassar, 2019). Recent scholarships are evident the leadership as a principal role in terms of their behavior exhibiting green values and in decision making respectively. Hence, green transformational leaders convey eco-friendly standards to their followers and convince them to track (M. Saleem et al., 2021; Wang, Zhou, & Liu, 2018). Most organizations have adopted green expressions and give maximum overall performance by handling waste & harmful substances (Melnik, Sroufe, & Calantone, 2003). Similarly, hotels can also organize employee training and customer services in the same disposition along with smart handling of waste and energy consumption (Rahman, Reynolds, & Svaren, 2012; Bohdanowicz, Zientara, & Novotna, 2011).

For the last many years, ecological trends in the hotel and tourism sector have remained emerging phenomena in research is evident (Zientara & Zamojska, 2018; Gürlek & Tuna, 2018; Kim & Choi, 2013; Siyambalapitiya, Zhang, & Liu, 2018; Robin, Pedroche, & Astorga, 2017; Novacka, K Picha, Topaloglu, & Švec, 2019; Mittal & Dhar, 2016; Jones, Hillier, & Comfort, 2016; Aragon-Correa, Martin-Tapia, & I. de la Torre-Ruiz, 2015; Hsiao & Chuang, 2016). Especially in developing countries, where environmental control has become a challenge and there is a need to observe changes in adopting nature-safety strategies by comparing developed and developing entities (OECD, 2013). According to a review analysis conducted by Yong, Yusliza, and

Fawehinmi (2019), From 2007 till now research intellectuals remained attracted to the eco-friendly work environment and the mechanism that prevails between ecological transformational leadership and innovativeness mechanism has remained as a “Black box” (X. Chen, Chen, Zhang, & He, 2023; Duan, Jan 2021) which need to find out. In-depth analysis is a pre-requisite to finding out the rooted significance of green transformational leadership involving green psychological constructs to help the hospitality sector to win the climate war with excellence in innovative manners.

Green psychological empowerment is desirable to be explored to understand the phenomena (Tariq, Jan, & Ahmad, 2016). So, there are many essential questions to be addressed like does green transformational leadership impact employees’ psychological behavior? Does transformational leadership influence green organizational innovativeness? To investigate employee green psychological empowerment mediates the relationship between green transformational leadership and dependent variable. Investigate that the green psychological capital moderates the relationship between the ecological behavior of fellows and the green innovation of association. Therefore, to bridge the scholarly gap, this empirical investigation is going to grant in the ocean of knowledge by examining green transformational leadership link with organizational green innovative outcomes in the presence of serial mediators, green psychological empowerment, and ecological behavior, with moderation impact of green psychological capital. The analysis outcomes will be proved to be helpful to leaders in hotels to understand the mechanism between them and employees which ultimately leads to unique innovativeness of firms. Theoretically, the expansion of RBV is being observed. Further scheme of the paper involved the review of past studies, and methodology part to elaborate the details of data collection, analysis, results, discussion, contributions, and limitations with future pathways.

2. LITERATURE INSIGHTS: THEORY, RELATIONSHIP, AND HYPOTHESES

2.1. Underpinning Theory

To understand the mechanism between green transformational leadership and green organizational innovation in the hotel sector in developing countries, we have applied the *Resource-Based theory (RBV)* of the firm. Originated by Penrose's (1959) revolutionary research work, RBV theory emphasizes the existence and significance of the inner resources of the organization for progress (Hameed, Zaman, Waris, & Shafique, 2021). Barney (1991) explained the theory of RBV that firms possessed resources that are “rarer, valuable, and impossible to imitate” and firms can utilize these intangible resources as strategic means to attain a competitive edge in organizational outcomes. In explaining the concept Amit & Schoemaker, (1993) also elaborate that these critical, strategic resources which are not substitutable lead towards sustainable performance and competitive superiority. By utilizing the RBV application we create a link between leadership and firm innovativeness. Accordingly, we pondered management and workers are the strategic resources a firm possessed. In the field of strategic management, this theory has become popular to investigate competitive advantages (Furrer, Thomas, & Goussevskaia, 2008).

Recent studies advised that to quote this aforementioned theory in the context of hospitality, organizations have to bind up their all semi-permanent assets and resources in a collective manner (Hossain, Hussain, Kannan, & Nair, 2021). During the collection of shreds of evidence from previous research, we found that scholars have contributed well in expanding the lenses of RBV and examined many previous as well as recent concepts under this theory. Like, for example, recently, strategic human resource management (Collins, 2021), the study of the community as a strategic resource of the firm (Gibson, Gibson, & Webster, 2021), and the study of green projects (Hameed et al., 2021) (Singh, Del Giudice, Chierici, & Graziano, 2020) are inclusive but still, there is a dearth to grasp especially under the green flag. So, we anticipate that green transformational leadership will impact green organizational innovation by creating direct and

indirect linkages through employees' psychological states under the umbrella of the resource-based view.

2.2. Green Transformational Leadership

Leadership in literature remained a hot topic for scholars and they recognized it as a critical element that affects creativity (Chang, Bai, & Li, 2015) and innovation. Green transformational leadership has been defined as the leader's trait to convince and encourage his/her co-workers to achieve green goals and behave in exceptional manners to perform in this regard (Chen et al., 2013). Emphasizing the importance of transformational leadership, literature not only recognized their positive result on innovativeness (Chen, et al., 2015) as well as they are known to develop creative ideas and convince the power of their workers towards revolution (Jung, Chow, & Wu, 2003). Recent scholarly articles highlighted green transformational leadership as a leader's behavior that plays a vital part to support a strong vision, inspiring, motivating, and providing backing toward the developmental requirements of employees to attain the ecological goals of firms (Chen & Chang, 2013; Mittal & Dhar, 2016).

2.2.1 Green Transformational Leadership and green psychological Empowerment

Spreitzer, (1995) explained psychological empowerment by way of the collective psychological state of an individual feeling “a sense of control” during work. And when this concept comes under the state of ensuring and doing tasks related to environmental concerns, this term can be transformed towards “Green psychological empowerment” of employees. It has been derived from the term, green employee empowerment which has explained that this concept emerges with the state of psychological empowerment under the bottom-line approach (Tariq et al., 2016). Because the time requires to involve green activities in every “bit & byte” of the organization through environment-friendly administration (Tariq et al., 2016). Though leaders have several boundaries within organizations like SOPs of institutions, policies, and practices of the human resource department, and other internal and social factors, they have influential capacities towards the employees' psychological empowerment perceptions.

(Pieterse, Van Knippenberg, Schippers, & Stam, 2010). Thus, Pieterse et al., (2010) empirically examine psychological empowerment as moderating element between transformational leadership, transactional leadership, and employee innovative behavior. According to their result, transformational leadership influences employee innovative behavior in positive manners only with the condition of high psychological empowerment and adversely, under the same condition transactional leadership impact negatively. So, there is a need to explore this newly emerging phenomenon in the prevailing green scenario, this research work is presenting the following framework to bridge the gap.

H1. Green transformational leadership has a significant and positive association with green psychological empowerment

2.3. Green psychological Empowerment and Ecological Behavior

In structuring the relationship between green psychological empowerment and ecological behavior, the philosophy of resource-based view delivers leverage as psychological empowerment demonstrated to be a strategic resource fit as competitive power that qualified under Barney's (1991) specific conditions i.e., "rare, non-sustainable & matchless". Psychological empowerment has been presented to be a managerial device through which organizational vision is to be shared to realize the goal line (Gautam & Ghimire, 2017). According to a study conducted by Yukl and Becker (2006) to attain sustainability, employees' empowerment is required to be used as a long-term strategy. Alongside this side, (Saleem, et al., 2017) confirmed that psychological - empowerment stands to be a key element of ecological behavior. Moreover, they stated that psychological empowerment creates a mechanism by way of which transformational nature leaders' impact positively on green behavior and turnover intentions of employees. So, to fill the literary gap, the following hypothesis is being presented:

H2. Green psychological empowerment has a positive relationship with the ecological behavior of employees

H3. Green Psychological Empowerment mediates the relationship between green transformational leadership and green organizational innovativeness

2.4. Ecological Behavior and Green Organizational Innovation

Employees' ecological behavior has become an emerging trend in the last few years. When members of the staff willingly absorb the environmental activities and behave in accordance apart from their obligations this is called "ecological behavior" (Daily, Bishop, & Govindarajulu, 2009). More valued employees keep themselves involved enthusiastically in green affairs (Paillé et al., 2013). Previous publications in the natural environmental domain refer green- innovation concept as production and process in an eco-friendly atmosphere (Albort-Morant & Carrion, 2016). In the same way, scholastic specialists (Delmas & Pekovic, 2018) certify that organizational innovativeness as a key driver to a firm's sustainable change can be successfully done by employees. So, it can be said that institutional environmental innovation depends upon the environmental safety behaviors of workers. In the beacon of the RBV, our prediction holds that ecological behavior and green innovation are organizational competitive sources as behaviors cannot be imitated by rivals and innovation holds uniqueness therefore both constructs qualify the conditions of the theory, ultimately leading toward the sustainable competitive outcomes with unbreakable innovativeness. So, our prediction is that:

H4. Ecological behavior has a positive significant relationship with green organizational innovation

H5. Ecological behavior mediates between green transformational leadership and green organizational innovation

2.5. Green psychological capital As Moderator.

Green team resilience has been acknowledged as a "captivating novel topic" by Eys et al., (2019) and is being introduced in the firms adopting green change. Literary individuals in the field of psychology recommended establishing green team resilience through training sessions and strategic supportive structured sessions (Alliger, et al., 2015; Shashi, Centobelli, Cerchione, & Ertz, 2020; Varajão, et al., 2021). To robust psychological capital, green team resilience has been studied as an outcome variable that gets influenced by green-transformational leaders and their results generate positive

conclusions (Çop, Olorunsola, & Alola, 2021) hence the significance is evident. Bandura, (1993) provided that the concept of self-efficacy is considered the state of confidence on own capabilities for realizing work opportunities. Additionally, individuals enriched with self-efficacy become more creative to introduce innovative products and possessed reliance on their abilities which is required to achieve the goal line (Hmieleski & Baron, 2008). Self-efficacy and resilience are the two constructs of psychological capital which a person possessed psychologically. The other two constructs are hope and optimization (Luthans, et al., 2007). Green self-efficacy and green

team resilience moderate the relationship between ecological behavior and organizational green innovation, so the importance of green psychological capital is vital. Still, there is a dearth of understanding and explaining these aforementioned norms. To fill this knowledge lacuna, we suggested the following:

H6. Green team resilience moderates the connectivity between ecological behavior and green organizational innovation

H7. Green self-efficacy moderates the relationship between ecological behavior and green organizational innovation

Theoretical Framework

Source: Author design

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Collection

Data was collected from five-star, four-star, and three-star hotels in Pakistan as Pakistan is listed among those developing countries in which the hospitality business is in growing age. A multi-stage data collection technique was used. In the first stage, clusters were made to select cities for data collection. In the second phase, a stratified random sampling technique was used for the selection of hotels as well as for data collection from hotel employees at all levels and in all departments. The self-administered survey questionnaire was used to accumulate data. As per Ruane's table (2005, p.109), the sample size was 500. SPSS process is the software to analyze the data.

3.2 Measurements

To conduct the survey, a questionnaire was formed based on measurement scales provided previously containing validly adopted scales. Which were then adapted according to the context of this paper and used. A 5-point Likert scale was used to evaluate the constructs. Green transformational leadership: the scale of 6-items was adopted by (Chen & Chang, 2013) to measure green transformational leadership. Ecological behavior: to measure ecological behavior extracted 16 items from Kaiser et al, (2007), Robertson & Barling, (2013) and Kim et al., (2016). Green psychological empowerment: Adopted from Akroush (2011) and Leonidou, Leonidou, Fotiadis, and Zeriti (2013) to measure Self-efficacy, we use Chen et al. (2015) measurement tool involving 6 items. And for green team resilience, we implement a scale from Mallak (1998) and its 7-items.Green

Innovation: 7 items measurements were used from Chen et al., (2006).

4. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Demographics Analysis

Overall data collection is done by both means like through Google form and through a self-administered way. Due to the pandemic lockdown, hotels were closed and only a few employees were present at their workplace. Limited numbers of responses were received from three types of hotels from three clusters. 80 responses were received through social media and only 235 were received manually .Out of these above-mentioned responses, 283 were able to analyze data. SPSS 23 Process was the program to analyze data of current research work. Before descriptive and inferential analysis, demographic analysis (Table 4.1-4.6) was done which shows mostly there were female respondents (69%) from five star hotel (70%) at managerial level job (43%) postgraduate (36%) aged within 36-45 years (59%) having more than 10 years of job experience (51%). These values indicated the aptitude of respondents. They seriously gave feedback.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics- Data Normality

In Descriptive analysis (Table 4.7), another test was performed which was to check data normality. As it is an assumption of data to be normal. Mean values indicate in the concerned table described that most respondents' choice was to remain strongly agreed

with the statements and values of skewness and kurtosis explained that data was normally distributed. As skewness and kurtosis values must remain between -2 to +2 (Aslam, 2021). Additionally, the histogram showed that there was no abnormality in the data set. So, it was a green indicator to further go ahead.

4.3 Reliability measurement

CronBach's Alpha is the tool to identify the reliability and internal consistency of the data set. And according to Cronbach, (1951) the threshold is greater than 0.70. Results in Table 4.8 elaborated that the data is purely reliable and perfectly consistent internally. Values of the CBA test of all variables remain between 0.708 to 0.911 which shows the data is good in reliability. This step pushes the analysis toward the next test.

4.4 Establishing Relationship between Variables: Correlation Analysis

The next step was to check the existence of relationships among variables. For this purpose correlation analysis was done. Correlation statistics are guided in three ways, first, it shows the strength of the relationship between variables, second, provided the direction of the relationship as it indicates the positive or negative mode of data, and thirdly it confirmed the significance of the relationship.

Table 4.9.

Correlations		GTL	GPE	EEB	OGI	Green PC
GTL	Pearson Correlation	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)					
	N	283				
GPE	Pearson Correlation	.645**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000				
	N	283	283			
EEB	Pearson Correlation	.655**	.631**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000			
	N	282	282	282		
OGI	Pearson Correlation	.702**	.550**	.653**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		

	N	282	282	282	282	
Green PC	Pearson Correlation	.706**	.732**	.595**	.799**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	282	282	282	282	282

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.9 clearly indicates that there existed a strong, positive, and significant relationship between variables. As Pearson correlation value in each column directs the strength of association between variables, sig. value identifying the existence of

significance and positive values demonstrating the direction of the relationship which is positive. Authentic significant value is less than 0.05 level and recent study correlation among variables is significant at the 0.01 level.

4.5 Regression Process Method

Table. 4.10: Hypotheses Check and mediation effect

Path 1. Outcome: GPE

Model Summary

R	R-sq	F	df1	df2	p
.6440	.4147	198.4248	1.0000	280.0000	.0000

Model

	Co.eff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
constant	.6693	.0677	9.8873	.0000	.5361	.8026
GTL	.5535	.0393	14.0863	.0000	.4762	.6309

Outcome: GOI

Model Summary

R	R-sq.	F	df1	df2	p
.7476	.5589	117.4227	3.0000	278.0000	.0000

Model

	Co.eff	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	.3572	.0877	4.0734	.0001	.1846	.5299
EEB	.4092	.0728	5.6226	.0000	.2659	.5525

DIRECT AND INDIRECT EFFECTS

Direct effect of X on Y

Effect	SE	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
.4656	.0583	7.9828	.0000	.3508	.5805

Indirect effect of X on Y

Effect	Boot SE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
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TOTAL	.2479	.0550	.1626	.3866
GPE	.0360	.0462	-.0577	.1251
EEB	.2118	.0435	.1344	.2995

Table 4.11 Moderation Effect

Outcome: GOI.

Model Summary

R	R-sq.	F	df1	df2	p
.7862	.6181	149.9490	3.0000	278.0000	.0000

Interactions:

Int_1 EEB X green team resilience

R-square increase due to interaction(s):

R2-chng	F	df1	df2	p
int_1 .0038	2.7766	1.0000	278.0000	.0968

Outcome: GOI

Model Summary

R	R-sq.	F	df1	df2	p
.8017	.6427	166.6695	3.0000	278.0000	.0000

Interactions:

Int_1 EEB X Green Self-efficacy

R-square increase due to interaction(s):

R2-chng	F	df1	df2	p
int_1 .0512	39.8217	1.0000	278.0000	.0000

Table 4.12. path Analysis

Hypotheses	Constructs	R-square	Co eff.	t-value	P-value	LLCI	ULCI	Remarks
H1	GTL > GPE	.4147	.5535	14.0863	.0000	.4762	.6309	Accepted
H2	GPE > EEB	.398	.043	13.601	.000			Accepted
H3	GTL>GPE>GOI	.0360	.4656	7.9828	.0000	-.0577	.1251	Rejected
H4	EEB > GOI	.5589	.4092	5.6226	.0000	.2659	.5525	Accepted
H5	GTL > EEB> GOI	.2118	.4656	7.9828	.0000	.1344	.2995	Accepted
H6	EEB*GTR>GOI	.6181	.8152	3.7671	.0000	.3892	1.2412	Accepted
H7	EEB*GSE>GOI	.0512	1.6285	9.5892	.0000	-.8678	-.4551	Accepted

The next step after finding out the correlation between variables is to check the hypothesis's acceptance or rejection and to find out is there any mediation exists, either moderating variables moderate the relationship. If yes, then how much moderation effect strengthens or weakening the relationship? To find out all related questions, the author analyzed data with the SPSS process by Hayes (2013)

According to the above-given values of SPSS process analysis by Hayes (2013) indicating t -value, significant value (P-Value), beta value (coefficient) and upper limit confidence interval and lower limits confidence interval (LLCI & ULCI) values are the indicating mechanism that proves the acceptance or rejection of hypotheses. According to the tables illustrated above (table 4.10-4.12), indicating values demonstrated that all hypotheses have been accepted on the bases of $t > 1.645$, $t > 1.965$ and $P > 0.05$ unless only one has been rejected which was green psychological empowerment mediates between green transformational leadership and green organizational innovativeness. R-square amount specified that change which moderating variable brought into the relationship. The direct and indirect path shows the mediation effect. Hayes (2013) introduced whether there existed mediation or not. No partial mediation occurred. So, the results established employee ecological behavior mediates the relationship between dependent and independent variables, but no mediation was found in the case of green psychological empowerment. For moderation outcomes, green team resilience and green self-efficacy moderate between employee ecological behavior and green organizational innovativeness.

5. Discussion & Conclusion

The term "Black Box" expressed by (Duan, Jan 2021) has become a beacon of knowledge in terms of finding out the prevailing mechanism between green transformational leadership and innovativeness of hotels and the results of the analysis aligned with literature that green transformational leadership has a relationship with the innovativeness of organization. But at the same time, while unveiling the hidden mechanism, this study provides an inside look at that organism. According to this, employees' ecological behavior worked as a mediator, and green

team resilience plus green self-efficacy played a moderating role between the ecological behavior of employees and collective green organizational innovativeness behavior. According to the result findings, green transformational leadership has a significant positive effect on green psychological empowerment of employees. Which means if transformational leaders empowered their subordinates in following and convincing the adoption of ecological aspects, the results will be positive gestures? But findings also indicated that green psychological empowerment is not a mediating (Gautam & Ghimire, 2017) factor between the prevailing relationship. In the same vein, green psychological capitals have an impactful moderating relationship between employee ecological behavior and green organizational innovativeness.

In this way, this current research paper is a slight struggle to unveil by emphasizing intangible resources of the firm under RBV theoretical grounds. Results alignment with literature will only be found under the behavior of employees and organizational innovation (Delmas & Pekovic, 2018) in separate studies. Studies of environmental studies have become an emerging trend and less researchers have worked to explore more about it. In the case of the psychological aspect, it is snubbed. So, the contribution remained rare as this work has become a source of understanding employees' stance on the psychological background at the individual level, and at the collective level while analyzing the organizational aspect of green innovativeness at the same time.

The analysis outcome revealed that the successful contribution of this research work has been done as this analysis finds out the all research questions asked to answer and bridge the gap in existing knowledge. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, the current investigation is in the list of initial shots to find out the association between transformational type of leadership and organizational innovative behavior in the presence of employee's psychological aspects on green grounds especially through considering psychological aspects of workers an intangible, strategic resource in hotel serving sector in Pakistan like a developing country. Psychological aspects have remained the less studied phenomenon in the service sector.

Inconclusive remarks, under the light of the above discussion and conclusive debate, environmental adaption inside and outside the organization is not a hard target that can't be achieved. Leaders have the power to emphasize and convince their subordinates through psychological empowerment and they can create a sense of responsibility in employees to accept the need for time. When an employee is psychologically equipped to work under specific conditions, it generates a skill and becomes psychological capital for them. When skilled workers individually give their best to create a green environment within the firm, they collectively coerce towards innovative behavior of the organization while adapting green behavior within every department of the organization. In a country like Pakistan, where the hospitality sector has to groom with fewer resources there is a need to recognize their insubstantial resources and to utilize them as a strategic & competitive edge to cope with the emerging environmental factors.

5.1 Theoretical Implication

The outcome analysis of this scholarly piece of work will prove to be a hard effort to enhance RBV theory by explaining new and ignored prevailing psychological phenomena within organizations. This research shed light on the emerging concept of green psychological empowerment and green psychological capital which have been presented as one of hidden competitive advantages which were ignored. A slight effort to realize the existence and power of transformational leaders' traits to convince their subordinates toward green attraction. Through this scholarly attempt, we tried to open the "black box" between leadership and innovativeness through the lens of a resource-based-view of the organizations,

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especially under the green flag which is an immense requirement of time.

5.2 Practical Implication

Along with theoretical enhancement, there is some practical advancement too. On the applied side, leaders on different stages like CEOs, COOs, General Managers, and managers at different levels will be able to realize the importance of every aspect inside and outside the organization as far as employees are concerned or it might the stakeholders. This study suggested leaders that sustain rivalry in the market, a realization of strategic elements is imperative. This cut-throat competition required to have a uniqueness in production and services as well as in reinforcing green behaviors. Leaders can achieve the highest position in the market if they convince, motivate, develop and maintain environment-friendly activities adoption and train their employees accordingly.

5.3 Limitations with future track

No study is without limitations, here are the followings:

1st: we studied all concepts in the light of one theory, "resource-based-view". Other theories can be applied and recommended. 2nd: in the list of developing countries many other countries are entitled so, another recommendation is to research other countries. 3rd: only the hospitality sector has been chosen in the service sector. Another sector can be touched on in future studies. 4th: in the analyses of green psychological capital, the rest of the two dimensions can be studied. 5th: only transformational leadership has been examined, other leadership styles can be added to the analysis. 6th: Sampling collection is done in only three cities in Pakistan, to expand generalizability, samples can be collected from other cities as well.

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